

Quantum Entropy Describing Bound Momentum and Wave Features?

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Classical statistical mechanics (for example a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas) seems to be governed by interactions which affect the momentum of a particle, but do not involve its wavelength \hbar/p actively in a calculation i.e. there are no interference effects. On the other hand, a quantum bound state involves both impulse hits which change the momentum (in a one dimensional problem), but also the associated wavelength which restricts the particle's presence for certain x regions i.e. there is a resolution.

In this note, we focus on the latter situation and attempt to formulate an entropy expression which incorporates both the momentum (impulse hits) and wave features in a manner different from: $S_p = -\sum_p a^*(p)a(p) \ln(|a^*(p)a(p)|)$ and $S_x = -\int dx W^*(x)W(x) \ln(|W^*(x)W(x)|)$ where $W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. We use the ground state wavefunction of the quantum oscillator as an example and first present an approximation based on resolution. For a quantum bound state, if the potential delivers an impulse which changes the particle into a p momentum state, then by translational invariance we consider it as having probabilities (resolution) to be at the peaks of $\cos(px)$. The overall probability for a given p , using $p=\hbar/\text{wavelength}$, is then approximated as:

$\hbar/(L2p) * |a(p)| / \{\sum_p |a(p)|\}$ (where $\hbar/(L2p)$ is $1/$ (the number of half wavelengths which fit into L).

This may be used in a Shannon's entropy scheme to yield:

$$S = -\sum_p \hbar/(2Lp) |a(p)| B \{ -\ln(B) + \ln(C) - \ln(p) + \ln(|a(p)|) \}$$

Where $B=1/\{\sum_p |a(p)|\}$ and $C=\hbar/2L$ with L being a cutoff length in the problem (to avoid using infinite). We apply this approach for the ground state of the harmonic oscillator.

Next we try to refine the approach by replacing $\hbar/(2Lp)$ with an x dependent probability:

$$|\cos(px)|/A(p) \text{ where } A(p) \text{ is a normalization over one crest} = A/p$$

We also consider the ground state oscillator result with this modification and then suggest a refinement i.e replace $\text{constant}1/p$ with $|\cos(px)|/p * \text{constant}2$.

Entropy and Momentum/Wave Considerations

Classical statistical mechanics seems to be based on interactions. For example, if one considers a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, there may be interparticle interactions as well as interactions with the particles in the wall. The volume is linked to the position of the wall particles which render interactions. In the classical case the interactions are of the form of impulse hits which change a particle's momentum. Wave considerations linked to $\text{wavelength}=\hbar/p$ do not usually come into play in calculations as there is no interference.

In the quantum bound state (one dimension), however, both are present and seem to have important effects. First the potential renders impulse hits which lead to a set of numbers $a(p)$ i.e. weights of various wave dynamical probabilities $\exp(ipx)$. Thus one has a wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. An interesting feature is that if $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ renders an impulse hit changing a particle to momentum p , then due to translational invariance ($\exp(ipx)$ is an eigenfunction of $-i\hbar d/dx$ where d/dx is the translational generator), the particle may be at a number of different locations with various probabilities. As a first step, we consider a symmetric situation so $\exp(ipx) \rightarrow 2\cos(px)$ (when one considers p and $-p$) and only consider the peak points of $\cos(px)$. In other words we focus on resolution due to the wavelength. We choose a cutoff length L (which may be 2 or 3 standard deviations for the ground state oscillator wavefunction which is a Gaussian $\exp(-.5 \sqrt{km} xx)$). We argue that the spatial probability within L , for wavelength $= \hbar/p$ is associated with

$$\hbar/p2L \quad ((1))$$

This is then multiplied by $|a(p)| / \{\sum_p a(p)\}$ ((2)) to produce an overall probability which may be used in a Shannon's entropy scenario.

Shannon's Entropy Scenario

Consider the case of a series of probabilities $p(i)$ with $0 < p(i) < 1$ such that $\sum_i P(i) = 1$. For a set of N trials where N is a very large number, one expects sequences linked with the following probability:

$$\text{Product over } i \quad P(i)^{NP(i)} \quad ((2))$$

A probability is $1/(\text{number of arrangements})$ so:

$$-\ln(\text{arrangements}) = \sum_i N P(i) \ln(P(i)) \quad \text{where } -\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$$

is called Shannon's entropy.

For the bound quantum state, we consider that impulse hits occur continuously due to a potential and that there is a probability $|a(p)| / \{\sum_p |a(p)|\}$ for a certain momentum and $\hbar/p2L$ for the position (due to translational invariance). We thus suggest a Shannon's entropy of (in a first approximation):

$$S = - \sum_p |a(p)| D/p \{ \ln(|a(p)|) - \ln(p) + \ln(D) \} \quad ((3))$$

where D is a constant $= (\hbar/2L) (1/\{\sum_p |a(p)|\})$

Ground State Harmonic Oscillator

For the ground state harmonic oscillator: $a(p) = C1 \exp(-.5pp/\sqrt{km}) > 0$ ((4)).

The ground state wavefunction is $C_2 \exp(-.5\sqrt{km} x)$ so the standard deviation is: $(km)^{-.25}$ ((5)). We choose $L=2*3*$ standard deviation with $L/2$ to the right of $x=0$ and $L/2$ to the left.

Given that we use, as a first approximation, the notion of resolution to determine allowed x points, we consider that all p values from 0 to $1 = L^2 p / \hbar^2$ represent a spatial probability of 1 i.e there is only 1 resolution point. Then ((3)) becomes:

$$S = - \int_{(0, \text{to } \hbar/2L)} (C_1/B) \exp(-pp/\{2\sqrt{km}\}) \{ \ln(C_1) - pp/\{2\sqrt{km}\} - \ln(B) \}$$

$$- \int_{\hbar/2L \text{ to infinite)} C_1 \exp(-pp/\{2\sqrt{km}\}) D/p \{ \ln(C_1) - pp/\{2\sqrt{km}\} - \ln(p) + \ln(D) \}$$

$$((5)) \quad \text{where } B = \int dp C_1 \exp(-pp/\{2\sqrt{km}\})$$

The integral in ((5)) may be performed numerically to yield a first approximation entropy for the ground state of a quantum oscillator.

More Refined Entropy Calculation

As a refinement to the above calculation, instead of simply using $\hbar/(2Lp)$ as probabilities for fixed x positions (resolution points) of a given p , one may consider each x point as having a probability of:

$$|\cos(px)| / A(p) \quad \text{where } A(p) = 1/p \int_{(0, 3.1.4)} \cos(y)dy = F/p \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{The new overall probability is the: } |a(p)| / \{ \text{Sum over } p |a(p)| \} * |\cos(px)| / (Fp) \quad ((7))$$

Thus $1/p$ appears again, but there is the extra $|\cos(px)|$ piece. This leads to a Shannon's entropy of:

$$S = - \text{Sum over } p \int_{(-L/2 \text{ to } L/2)} |\cos(px)| |a(p)| D/p \{ \ln(|a(p)|) - \ln(p) + \ln(|\cos(px)|) + \ln(D) \} \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{where } D \text{ is a constant} = (\hbar/2L) (1/\{ \text{Sum over } p |a(p)| \}) * (1/F)$$

This integral may also be performed numerically.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we propose a different Shannon's entropy form for a quantum bound state (i.e. different from $S_p = - \text{Sum over } p P(p) \ln(P(p))$ and $S_x = - \int dx P(x) \ln(P(x))$ which incorporates both momentum changes and wave effects. As a first approximation we consider a

given p (momentum) as being associated with resolution x points separated by half a wavelength. Thus we have a probability of $|a(p)| / \{\sum \text{over } p |a(p)|\} * p * \text{constant}$ where $p * \text{constant} = 1 / (\text{number of resolution points which fit into a length } L) = 1 / \text{number of half wavelength}$. We choose L as a cutoff length instead of using infinite. We apply this approach to the ground state oscillator and consider the number of resolution points as 1 for small p values (until half the wavelength matches the length L i.e. $p=0$ to $\hbar/2L$). After that, large p are associated with higher numbers of resolution points i.e. a probability of $\hbar/(2Lp)$. The integrals may be performed numerically.

We then refine the entropy calculator using a probability associated with each p, x as:

$$|a(p)| / \{\sum \text{over } p |a(p)|\} * |\cos(px)| / (Fp) \quad (\text{where the constant } F \text{ is defined in ((7))).$$

This then leads to the Shannon's entropy expression ((8)) which may again be integrated over both p and x numerically.